

Salts of Substituted Malonic Acids

A. M. TALATI and B. V. SHAH

Chemistry Department, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda.

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Cobalt (II), Copper (II), Zinc (II) and Manganese (II) salts of substituted benzylidene malonic acids are prepared and their magnetic moment at room temperature is determined.

ALTHOUGH many substituted malonic acids and their salts are known, only few references are found in the literature on their transition metal salts. Co (II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn (II) and Mn (II) salts of malonic and substituted malonic acids have been studied by Milner and Pratt¹, Ranadae and Subba Rao², Ives and Riley³, Ragan⁴, Graddon⁵, Dingle⁶, Cohn and Townsend⁷, Grey⁸, Mata Prasad, Kanekar, Walvekar and Khanolkar⁹, etc. We present here our studies on the salts of cobalt, copper, zinc and manganese with benzylidene malonic acid and its derivatives (I).

Experimental

Substituted malonic acids :

Benzylidene malonic acid was prepared from benzaldehyde and malonic acid by the method of Fujiwara and Naruse¹⁰. *o*- and *p*-chlorobenzylidene malonic acids were prepared from malonic acid and *o*- and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde respectively by the method of Pandya and Pandya¹¹. Further, *p*-methoxybenzylidene malonic acid and *p*-nitrobenzylidene malonic acid were prepared from malonic acid and anisaldehyde and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde by the methods of Pandya and Vahidya¹² and Marckwald¹³ respectively.

Cobalt, copper, zinc and manganese salts : Partition method :

Substituted malonic acid dissolved in ether was added to the solution of metal acetate dissolved in water (ligand : metal : : 1,5 ; 1). The solution was stirred at low speed for 2 hrs. at low temperature and left overnight. The ether layer was separated and the precipitates were filtered, washed with water, acetone and ether and dried. The colour, m.p., analysis etc. of these compounds are presented in Tables 1 to 4.

The mass magnetic susceptibility of these complexes was determined at room temperature on Gouy's magnetic balance. The calculated values of magnetic moment are also presented in those tables.

Results and Discussion

These salts contain metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1 and are represented as (II).

Cobalt salts are pink in colour, indicating 6-coordinate structure 3d⁷. Co (II) in weak octahedral field has a T-ground state which carries orbital moment. Magnetic moment observed for these salts (5.11 to 5.31 B.M.) is in the range expected for weak octahedral field. However, 6-coordination cannot be reached in some salts unless polymeric structure is assumed. Relative insolubility of these salts in water, alcohol, acetone, etc. also favour such a structure.

Copper salts possess the magnetic moment of 1.80 to 2.18 B.M. Copper salts of various dicarboxylic acids are known to have abnormally low value of magnetic moment¹⁴⁻¹⁷. However, copper salts under investigation do not show such low values of magnetic moment. Hence spin-spin interaction through the formation of binuclear species cannot be assumed to take place in these salts.

Manganese salts possess the magnetic moment of 6.09 to 6.13 B.M. The moment is in the range expected for 6-coordinate Mn (II). (The ground state is A_{1g} which has no orbital contribution to magnetic moment). Pink colour of the salts also indicates the formation of 6-coordinate structure.

TABLE I—COBALT SALTS OF SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE MALONIC ACIDS Co (ANION)AQ_n

No.	substituted benzylidene malonate ion ; n = substituent=	colour	m. pt. (°C)	formula	Analysis							
					%C found	%H found	%Co found	%C reqd	%H reqd	%Co reqd	magnetic moment (B.M.)	
1.	—	4	pink	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₈ Co	37.6	4.01	18.6	37.4	4.36	18.4	5.31
2.	<i>o</i> -chloro	3.5	pink	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O _{7.5} Cl Co	34.2	3.33	16.2	34.6	3.46	17.0	5.11
3.	<i>p</i> -chloro	4.5	pink	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O _{8.5} Cl Co	33.4	3.91	15.6	32.9	3.84	16.2	5.17
4.	<i>p</i> -methoxy	2	pink	>300	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₇ Co	41.6	3.90	18.6	41.9	3.81	18.7	5.24
5.	<i>p</i> -nitro	4	pink	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ O ₁₀ NC ₂ O	32.5	3.35	15.9	32.8	3.55	16.1	5.29

TABLE 2—COPPER SALTS OF SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE MALONIC ACIDS Cu(ANION)AQ_n

No.	substituted benzylidene malonate ion ; n= substituent=	colour	m. pt. (°C)	formula	Analysis						Magnetic moment (B.M.)	
					%C found	%H found	%Cu found	%C reqd	%H reqd	%Cu reqd		
1.	<i>p</i> -methoxy	2.5	green	246 (d)	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O _{7.5} Cu	39.7	3.88	18.9	40.2	3.96	19.3	1.80
2.	<i>p</i> -nitro	3	blue	251 (d)	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₉ NCu	34.7	2.87	17.9	34.0	3.12	18.0	2.18

TABLE 3—ZINC SALTS OF SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE MALONIC ACIDS Zn (ANION)AQ_n

No.	substituted benzylidene malonate ion ; n= substituent=	colour	m. pt. (°C)	formula	Analysis						
					%C found	%H found	%Zn found	%C reqd	%H reqd	%Zn reqd	
1.	—	2.5	white	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O _{6.5} Zn	41.1	3.31	21.1	39.9	3.66	21.8
2.	<i>o</i> -chloro	2	white	249(d)	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₆ ClZn	37.7	2.30	19.7	36.8	2.76	20.0
3.	<i>p</i> -methoxy	1.5	white	>300	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O _{6.5} Zn	43.3	3.23	20.6	42.2	3.52	20.9
4.	<i>p</i> -nitro	3	pale yellow	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₉ NZn	33.8	3.06	18.5	33.9	3.10	18.5

TABLE 4—MANGANFSE SALTS OF SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE MALONIC ACIDS Mn(ANION)AQ_n

No.	substituted benzylidene malonate ion ; n= substituent=	colour	m. pt. (°C)	formula	Analysis						magnetic moment (B.M.)	
					%C found	%H found	%Mn found	%C reqd	%H reqd	%Mn reqd		
1.	—	2	pale yellow	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₆ Mn	42.6	3.46	19.6	42.7	3.56	19.5	6.12
2.	<i>o</i> -chloro	2	white	296(d)	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₆ ClMn	38.0	2.88	18.2	38.0	2.85	17.4	6.10
3.	<i>p</i> -chloro	1	pale yellow	>300	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₅ ClMn	40.2	2.11	18.7	40.3	2.35	18.5	6.09
4.	<i>p</i> -methoxy	2	pale yellow	>300	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₇ Mn	42.4	3.79	18.4	42.5	3.86	17.7	6.13
5.	<i>p</i> -nitro	3.5	pale yellow	>300	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O _{9.5} NMn	33.3	3.52	16.1	34.0	3.40	15.6	6.11

(I)

(II)

R=	M=Co	M=Cu	M=Zn	M=Mn
a ; C ₆ H ₅	n= 4	n= —	n= 2.5	n= 2
b ; <i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	3.5	—	2	2
c ; <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	4.5	—	—	1
d ; <i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	2	2.5	1.5	2
e ; <i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4	3	3	3.5

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